

**A LITERARY REVIEW ON CHARAKOKTA DEEPANIYA MAHAKASHAYA DRAVYAS
IN ASTANGA HRIDAYA SAMHITA****Dr. Shashi Tiwari^{*1}, Dr. Neha Singh², Dr. Rishabh Jain³**

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ABSTRACT

Ayurveda is a holistic science which focus on maintaining health of an individual and also on cure of disease too. In both these functions ayurveda mainly concentrate on correction of Agni (Jatharagni) and extinguishing of Aama (toxic material formed after metabolism of food).The work of Agni or fire is to burn everything, likewise it also burn Aama in body and also corrects the Jatharagni so that proper digestion of food takes place .By proper digestion proper Aahar Rasa will be formed, by proper Aahar Rasa all other dhatus (Rasa, Rakta, Mansa, Meda, Asthi, Majja, Shukra) will formed in appropriate manner and Doshas will also remain balanced and excretion of Mutra (urin), Purish (stool)and Swed(sweat)takes place properly. For correction of Agni there is unique composition of ten (10) Dravyas in Charaka Samhita also known as Deepaniya Mahakashaya. These dravyas not only used in medicinal purpose to correct Agni of a person, singly or in combination of two (2) or more Dravyas like Trikatu, Panchakola, Shadadushana etc and also in majority of different Aushadhiya Yogas and also in the preparation of Aahara in kitchen in Indian life style for flavour and easy digestion of food. These Dravyas are Pippali, Pippalimool, Chavya, Chitraka, Naagara, Ajamoda, Maricha, Amlavetasa, Bhallataka and Hingu. The medicine or yoga which contain Deepan dravyas are best during any treatment. So, Acharya Vaagabhatta have used these Deepaniya dravyas in his majority yoga. After Nidaana Parivarjana, for treatment of any disease Deepana - Pachana and Anuloman is primary important step.

KEYWORDS: Deepaniya Mahakashay, Deepana, Aama, Astanga Hridaya Samhita Aushadhiya Yoga.

INTRODUCTION

Deepaniya Mahakashaya term is given by Acharya Charaka in Charaka Samhita Sutra Sthan 4th Chapter Shadvirechanashatashritiya Adhyaya. Acharya Charaka has given 50 Mahakashaya in this chapter. Each Mahakashaya contain 10 dravyas or herbs in it, so also known as Charaka Dashemani. In these 50 Mahakashaya one is Deepaniya Mahakashaya.

Deepan: The Word Deepana literally means kindling, inflaming, setting a fire. In human biology, it means stimulating digestion. Deepan is a pacification treatment for kapha dosa. It is an essential prerequisite before

therapeutic emesis (vaman) and therapeutic purgation (virechan). The word Deepana is derived from the word deepa which means building the fire with nich or lyu suffix.

Deepaniya Mahakashaya have following 10 herbs in it. They are Pippali, Pippalimool, Chavya, Chitraka, Shringavera (Shunthi), Amlavetasa, Maricha, Ajamoda, Bhallatakasthi, Hinguniryas.

Sr. No.	Dravya	Botanical Name	Guna	Rasa	Veerya	Vipaka	Karma
1	Pippali	Piper longum	Laghu, Snigdha, Teekshn	Katu	Anushna- sheet	Madhur	Kafavaatshamaka
2	Pippalimool	Piper longum	Laghu, Ruksh	Katu	Usna	Katu	Kafavaatshamaka
3	Chavya	Piper retrofractum	Laghu, Ruksh	Katu	Usna	Katu	Kafavaatshamaka
4	Chitraka	Plumbago zeylanica	Laghu, Ruksh, Teekshn	Katu	Usna	Katu	Kafavaatshamaka
5	Shringavera	Zingiber officinale	Laghu, Snigdha	Katu	Usna	Madhur	Kafavaatshamaka
6	Amlavetasa	Garcinia pedunculata	Laghu, Ruksh	Amla	Usna	Amla	Kafavaatshamaka
7	Maricha	Piper nigrum	Laghu, Teekshn	Katu	Usna	Katu	Kafavaatshamaka
8	Ajamoda	Carum roxburghienum	Laghu, Ruksh Teekshn	Katu, Tikta	Usna	Katu	Kafavaatshamaka
9	Bhallataka	Semicarpus anacardium	Laghu, Snigdha, Teekshn	Katu, Tikta, Kashay	Usna	Madhur	Kafavaatshamaka
10	Hingu	Ferula northex Bairs	Laghu, Snigdha, Teekshn	Katu	Usna	Katu	Kafavaatshamaka

Aama: Aama is a key concept in the ayurvedic understanding of physiology, pathology and therapeutics. Rather than being a single entity or substance, Aama denotes the abnormal or impaired process of digestion and metabolism that leads to builds up of toxic by-products, which can't be neutralised or eliminated by the body.

Definition and Synonym of Deepana- The diet or medicine or process which stimulates digestion is called Deepana. Sha. Sa. Pu. Kh. 4/1. Deepana process stimulates digestion at a primary level.

By virtue of their Rasa, Guna, Veerya and Vipaka they do mainly Deepana work that is they increase the Jatharaagni (digestive Fire) so digestion of food becomes proper and no Aama or raw Aahara Ras is created.

Majority of diseases causes due to Jatharagnimand (low digestive fire). By Jatharagnimand no food is digested properly and Aama is generated. Aama is the root cause of disease in our body. So, our primary duty is to increase our digestive fire by taking the Deepaniya Mahakashaya.

Astanga Hridaya Samhita is divided into 6 sthaanas.

1st	2nd	3rd	4th	5th	6th
Sutra Sthaana 30 Adhyaaya	Shaarira Sthaana 6 Adhyaaya	Niddana Sthaana 16 Adhyaaya	Chikitsa Sthaana 22 Adhyaaya	Kalpa-Siddhi Sthaana 6 Adhyaaya	Uttara Sthaana 40 Adhyaaya

MATERIAL AND METHODS: Subject matter is collected from following

1. Astanga Hridaya
2. Dravyaguna-Vigyan
3. Shabdakosha
4. Different Article and online platforms

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Sr. No.	Yoga	Dravya (Herbs)	Shlok No.	Page No.
1	Shringavera Ambu	Shunthi	A.H.Su.3/23	29
2	Panchakola Churna	Pippali, Pippalimoola, Chavya, Chitraka, Shunthi	A.H.Su.3/46	32
3	Deepana Dravya – example -1	Hingu	A.H.Su.6/153	65
4	Deepana Dravya - example -2	Shunthi	A.H.Su.6/163	66
5	Deepana Dravya – example -3	Pippali, Pippalimoola, Chavya, Chitraka, Shunthi	A.H.Su.6/167	66
6	Virechana Dravya	Chitraka (Prabhava)	A.H.Su.9/26	81
7	Katu Varga Dravya	Hingu, Maricha, Pippali, Pippalimoola, Chavya, Chitraka, Shunthi	A.H.Su.10/30	84
8	Atisthaulya Chikitsa - 1	Shunthi	A.H.Su.14/24	102
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10	Atisthaulya Chikitsa -3	Hingu, Chitraka	A.H.Su.14/25	102

11	Nasya-Gana Shirovirechaka Aushadha	Shunthi, Maricha, Pippali	A.H.Su.15/4	104
12	Ushakadi Gana	Hingu	A.H.Su.15/23	106
13	Vatsakadi Gana	Maricha, Ajamoda, Hingu, Pippali, Pippalimoola, Chavya, Chitraka, Shunthi	A.H.Su.15/34	106
14	Vachadi Gana	Shunthi	A.H.Su.15/35	106
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27	Snanottara Churnadi Prayoga	Hingu, Pippali, Pippalimoola, Chavya, Chitraka, Shunthi	A.H.Sha.2/41, 42	182
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486	Netra Roga Nashaka Potali	Maricha	A.H.U.S.16/5	504
487	Kafaja Abhisyanda Chikitsa -1	Shunthi	A.H.U.S.16/17	505
488	Kafaja Abhisyanda Chikitsa -2	Shunthi, Maricha, Pippali	A.H.U.S.16/18	505
489	Netraadhimantha Chikitsa	Shunthi, Maricha, Pippali	A.H.U.S.16/24	505
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507	Kafaja Osta Roga Chikitsa	Shunthi, Maricha, Pippali	A.H.U.S. 22/8	525
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CONCLUSION

Deepaniya Mahakashaya functions both psychologically and somatically, initiating the Adya Awastha of digestion. These Dravyas play a crucial role in activating Jatharagni and extinguish Aama (Indigested Aahara Rasa). Separate description of Deepaniya mahakashaya is not in Astanga Hridaya Samhita, and these Dravyas are

found in Yogas of acharya Vaagabhatta Samhita (Astanga Hridaya) which act as Deepana Dravyas and Aama shamana Dravya's both. Deepaniya Mahakashaya Dravyas act by Prabhava (Effect). These Yoga or Dravyas had used how many times in Astanga Hridaya Samhita is in following table.

Sr. No.	Dravya	Number of Times Used
1	Pippali	316
2	Shunthi	333
3	Maricha	209
4	Chitraka	165
5	Hingu	69
6	Pippalimoola	76
7	Chavya	74
8	Bhallataka	37
9	Amlavetasa	22
10	Ajamoda	13

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